

MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF BREAST CANCER

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ABSTRACT:- Now-a-days, breast cancer is a disease that significantly impacts women. Breast cancer has surpassed lung cancer as the most often reported cancer in women worldwide, according to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) in December 2020. If cancer is found in the early stages, the likelihood that someone will survive is increased. This paper recap the survey on breast cancer diagnosis using various Machine Learning (ML) methods, which are used to boost the accuracy predicting cancer. The paper shows the data visualisation and performance differentiations between different ML algorithms like, Random Forest (RF), Naive Bayes (NB), Multilayer Perceptron, Decision Tree (DT), K- Nearest Neighbours (KNN), and Logistic Regression (LR). The major goal is to evaluate the model's performance, and tools like recall, F1-score, precision, and accuracy are employed to do so.

Keywords : Breast Cancer, K-Nearest Neighbour (K-NN), Random Forest (RF), Naive Bayes (NB), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Logistic regression (LR).

INTRODUCTION:- The most common illness that kills women's breast cancer. Tumour classification allows for analysis of breast cancer. It includes both malignant and benign tumours. To identify tumours, doctors performed a thorough examination. But even for experts, it can be challenging to identify tumours. The ability of ML algorithms to diagnose cancer has been proved by researchers, who seek to employ them to determine whether or not a patient will survive. In 2021, there will be 963,000 deaths of women, according to an estimate by the World Health Organization (WHO). Breast cancer is more common in women than in males, while it can happen in both. Breast cancer cases are expected to reach 17.3 lakhs in 2021, according to a new estimate from the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR). An average of one woman develops breast cancer every four minutes. Any man or woman can be treated for breast cancer in its early stages if they are aware of it. The development of aberrant cells that are genetically altered, spread throughout the body, and cause death in breast cancer patients. In this study, datasets used to develop and evaluate machine learning models for predicting breast cancer are examined.

3- Materials & Methods:- In this section, we have used the following materials and methods to implement the various ML algorithms.

3.1-DATASET USED:- In this paper, Wisconsin Breast Cancer Diagnosis dataset used from “[https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/breast+cancer+wisconsin+\(diagnostic\)](https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/breast+cancer+wisconsin+(diagnostic))” UCI for building the proposed MLP model. The implementation is executed on Google Colab. The dataset has 31 columns, including 1 target attribute for the proposed model's design and 30 features regarding the cancer cell. Description of the attributes is give in Table 2.

Table 2: Dataset Description

Attributes Name	Description
Id	“Id of an patient”
Diagnosis	“It shows whether the tumour is Benign or Malignant”
Radius_mean	“Mean of radius of breast”
Texture_mean	“Mean of texture of breast”
Perimeter_mean	“Mean of perimeter of breast”
Area_mean	“Mean of area of breast”
Smoothness_mean	“Mean of smoothness of breast”
Compactness_mean	“Mean of compactness of breast”
Concavity_mean	“Mean of concavity of breast”
Concave_points_mean	“Mean of concave points of breast”
Symmetry_mean	“Mean of symmetry of breast”
Fractal_dimension_mean	“Mean of fractal dimension of breast”
Radius_se	“Standard error of radius”
texture_se	“Standard error of texture”
Perimeter_se	“Standard error of perimeter”
Area_se	“Standard error of area”
smoothness_se	“Standard error of smoothness”
Compactness_se	“Standard error of compactness”
concavity_se	“Standard error of concavity”
Concavity_points_se	“Standard error of concavity points”

Symmetry_se	“Standard error of symmetry”
Fractal_dimension_se	“Standard error of fractal dimension”
Radius_worst	“Worst radius of breast”
Texture_worst	“Worst texture of breast”
Perimeter_worst	“Worst perimeter of breast”
Area_worst	“Worst area of breast”
Smoothness_worst	“Worst smoothness of breast”
Compactness_worst	“Worst compactness of breast”
Concavity_worst	“Worst concavity of breast”
Concave point_worst	“Worst concavity points of breast”
Symmetry_worst	“Worst symmetry of breast”
Fractal_dimension_worst	“Worst fractal dimension of breast”

3-2- Method Used:- Methods used for the proposed work and comparison of proposed model with other ML techniques will be discussed in next subsections.

3.2-1 Supervised Learning :- Supervised learning is a ML algorithm which works on labelled data. An external Supervision is required for this learning . In this , Labelled data may have input and output data which will help the machine to make accurate predictions . In this we have to train the data accordingly and after that we have to test the data for prediction and check the accuracy . Usually we take 80% as training data and 20% as testing data. It is used for both classification and regression algorithms.

3.2.2 Steps for designing the Machine Learning model.

3.2.2.1 Data preprocessing. In this step , we have to clean the dataset . If the dataset is having any missing values then we will have to fill the missing values in it.

3.2.2.2 Categorical Data :- Categorical data are the variables which are having non-numeric data. If we have to apply machine learning algorithms , then we have to convert it into numeric data. In this dataset, benign will be 0 and malignant will be 1.

3.2.2.3 Splitting the data :- We usually split the dataset into testing and training purposes. In this dataset we divide training data will be 80% and testing data will be 20%

3.2.2.4 Feature Scaling :- Magnitudes, units, and range are highly variable features in the dataset. As a result, we must equalise the size of all features. Scaling is a way to achieve this.

3.2.2.5 Model Selection :- In this we have to apply all the machine learning techniques to select the model. We will check the accuracy of all the models and select the model accordingly.

3.2.3 Machine Learning Algorithms :-

3.2.3.1 Logistic Regression :-One of the supervised machine learning techniques is the logistic regression algorithm. It typically displays the probability, which ranges from 0 to 1. This algorithm would forecast the results of categorical dependent variables. Between 0 and 1, it forms an S-shaped curve. And there, the sigmoid function is employed.

3.2.3.2 - Support Vector Machine :- A vector machine is used to generate a decision boundary that can manage n-dimensional two classes. so that in the future, we can rapidly and easily classify new data points. The choice boundary has the name of a hyperplane. Both linear and rbf kernels have been used in this.

3.2.3.3 - Decision Tree;-Decision trees are the supervised ML technique used for classification and prediction. Rules and nodes are the two halves of the D-tree algorithm. In many cases, a D-tree is a tree structure with nodes denoting the characteristics being tested, branches denoting the test's emission, and leaf nodes denoting the impact of each test on a class label. For the aim of identifying breast cancer, its leaf nodes are divided into benign and malignant categories. There are several rules that can be used to assess whether a tumour is benign or malignant.

3.2.3.4 Random Forest :-An algorithm for supervised classification is the RF algorithm. The Random Forest technique can manage the missing values in this classifier if we use more trees in the forest. We already dealt with the dataset's missing attribute values. If it contains many trees, the overfitting issue won't arise, and the model can handle categorical data. In this instance, categorical data such as benign and malignant will be translated to 0 and 1, respectively.

3.2.3.5 K-Nearest Neighbour :- Utilising the K-NN method, similar new data points are categorised. It can be categorised after the new data points appear. The underlying assumptions of the K-NN algorithm are independent of the data since it is a non-parametric approach. It keeps the dataset and then uses it to classify because it does not immediately learn from the training data. For this reason, it is sometimes referred to as the lazy learner algorithm.

3.2.3.6 Naive Bayes :- An approach to supervised machine learning is the Naive Bayes algorithm. The Bayes theorem provides the basis for it. It aids with classification problems. One of the classification algorithms that can predict results fast is the Naive Bayes Classifier since it enables the quick development of machine learning models. It provides predictions based on the likelihood of an object because it is a probabilistic classifier.

3.2.3.7 Multi-Layer Perceptron(MLP):-An artificial forward neural network that creates a set of outputs from a set of inputs is called a multilayer perceptron (MLP). The directed graph connecting the input and output layers of the MLP consists of several layers of input nodes. Backpropagation is

used by MLP to train the network. One of the deep learning techniques is MLP. In this we have, import the data with 31 columns. And then we applied the dense layer of 32 nodes and the input shape will be 29. and after that we have to double the hidden layers till 128 and the function used will be “relu”. and decrease accordingly till one output layer. In the output layer we will use the function sigmoid. Then we have to compile the model with metrics=['accuracy'] ,optimizer='adam', loss “Binary_crossentropy”. After That we have to compile the model with epochs 150, batchsize=5 , shuffle =False. then calculate the accuracy.

4. RESULT :-In this table ,we have compared the method which i have implemented.

Table 2: Comparison Table

Methods Used	Accuracy	Precision	Re-call	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	95.61%	96%	97%	96%
K Nearest Neighbour	95.61%	94%	99%	96%
Decision Tree	93.85%	97%	93%	95%
Random Forest	94.73%	97%	94%	95%
Guassian Naive Bayes	91.22%	93%	93%	93%
MLP	97.36	95%	97%	96%

Experimental tools:- For implementing the algorithms of Machine learning. We have used the various experimental tools as shown in table.

Table 3: Experimental tools

Tools	Google colab
Dataset sources	www.kaggle.com
Libraries used	Numpy, Pandas, Matplotlib, Sklearn , keras

Figures:-In these graphs , we have compared the various parameters like F1-score, precision, accuracy, recall of all calculations which I have implemented. At last we have compared the accuracy of all the algorithms.

Figure-1 :- Logistic Regression

Figure 1 shows the evaluation results for logistic regression with respect to F1 Score, Accuracy, Recall, Precision.

Figures-2:- K-Nearest Neighbour

Figure 2 shows the evaluation results for K-Nearest Neighbour with respect to F1 Score, Accuracy, Recall, Precision.

Figure-3:- Decision Tree

Figure 3 shows the evaluation results for Decision Tree with respect to F1 Score, Accuracy, Recall, Precision.

Figure -4:-Random Forest.

Figure 4 shows the evaluation results for Random Forest with respect to F1 Score, Accuracy, Recall, Precision.

Figure-5 :-Gaussian Naive Bayes

Figure 6 shows the evaluation results for Gaussian Naive Bayes with respect to F1 Score, Accuracy, Recall, Precision.

Figure-6 :- Multi-Layer Perceptron

Figure 6 shows the evaluation results for Multi-Layer Perceptron with respect to F1 Score, Accuracy, Recall, Precision.

Figure 7 :- Accuracy Comparison

Figure 1 shows the evaluation results for Accuracy with respect to Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbour, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Gaussian Naive Bayes and Multi-Level Perceptron.

5. Conclusion:- This paper is on breast cancer detection, we introduce you to different machine learning methods. The goal of our study was to address the Wisconsin breast cancer dataset by evaluating and visualising machine learning predictions. Multi-layered perceiver. We concluded that MLP is an algorithm that gives us an accurate breast cancer detection result with an accuracy of 97.36%.

6. Future Scope :- In future, we will work on various deep learning models and we will take the new disease dataset and will work on it. We will try to maximise the accuracy by using machine learning and deep learning models. So that they would give a good result which will help doctors to save the life of the patients.

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